

ADOPTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EMPLOYEE RECRUITMENT

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a technology that is growing in popularity every year. In software, development and a variety of other areas of information technology, intelligent and self-learning systems are used. Artificial intelligence is very far from human cognition, despite the fact that artificial intelligence is still a long way off make difficult decisions. Artificial intelligence software is the most adaptable solution for a wide range of business requirements. It opens up new possibilities for automation of processes that do not need much creativity and can thus be completed by a computer. The ability of artificial intelligence to analyze large data, volumes and quickly estimate available options enables process automation. A business, a corporation, or a firm requires quality personnel to achieve the goals that they have set for themselves in order to succeed in this competent era. All companies seek workers who are enthusiastic, willing and dynamic to stay competitive in this digital age. Comprehensive recruiting organizations should attract the best applicants to help them administer the new world and change business conditions. As a result, the most of an organization's recruiting policy is a vital component in attracting professional workers who can be more productive and competitive in achieving job goals as a major feature of the organization. The recruitment approach appears to rely on decision-making data analysis. Artificial intelligence (AI) adoption steps are influenced significantly by the analysis, which is referred to as such. The mission of artificial intelligence is to develop human intelligence by means of automation. Artificial intelligence has various applications in HR technology, including talent acquisition, assessment of applicants, staff participation and employee growth. The article ends with a suggestion for a newly developed recruitment technique. The main objective of the article is to examine how artificial intelligence is used when recruiting employees. The study found that senior executive HR had the strongest opinions on employing artificial intelligence to evaluate applicant resumes rather than human reviewers.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence, Recruitment, Human Resources, Technology and Employees and adoption.

INTRODUCTION

The digital revolution in this industry and the introduction of technology have reached a turning point. This is known as the "smart industry," which is how the fourth industrial revolution is described. The term "fourth industrial revolution," which was coined by Professor Schwab, enables a smart corporation to obtain the best commercial outcomes. As a result, cutting-edge technology like artificial intelligence and its subsets have been implemented into almost all functional facets of government, including human resource management. The current study aims to investigate how human resources experts and workers feel about AI technology. The study focuses on artificial intelligence views among participants and attempts to understand

emerging artificial intelligence technologies used in departments of human resources. This paper examines Artificial Intelligence and its increasing impact in the recruitment industry. In particular, the implementation of artificial intelligence impacts both employers and candidates during the recruiting process. This includes all aspects of the hiring process, including the initial job posting, candidate searching, and finally, interviewing and evaluating prospects. The objective is to identify the preferable strategy that recruiters, both internal and external consultancies, should employ when making hiring in reaction to impending changes in the industry. Interviews with business experts were conducted, which were then compared to employee and job seeker expectations before assessing the trends of an observation. The results of this main study were compared to the body of prior knowledge. As a result, this study suggests that a fresh approach to hiring be used. Teams will be able to improve the calibre and efficacy of their talent acquisition strategies thanks to this approach, which will need significant organisational and technological changes in recruiting operations. As a result, the structured hiring procedure will switch from a trial-and-error approach to a test-for-success one. The creation of intelligent machines by humans is the most basic form of artificial intelligence. With the ultimate goal of enabling computers to carry out jobs that people typically carry out, AI will operate and respond in a manner similar to that of humans. AI excels in terms of speed and accuracy. This article's main objective is to look into how artificial intelligence impacts hiring practises. The research frequently sheds light on how businesses are hiring for artificial intelligence (AI). To further explore the phrase, this study only uses secondary sources, such as conceptual records, peer-reviewed journal papers, books, and websites.

ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN RECRUITMENT PRACTICE

The management must work dynamically, since the main factor in all operations is manpower as an important production factor in organisational performance. Among all management roles, human resource managers face the difficult challenge of recruiting skilled candidates who have the necessary skill set to fit the work specifications in order to fulfill the organization's goals and objectives. Human resource managers must consider the methods, roles, and requirements of organizations in order to prepare the recruiting pool for young millennial that can fit into the organization. Despite the fact that artificial intelligence has been around since antiquity, numerous blogs and papers focused on AI's position in recruiting in 2019. Discussions about the potential applications of Artificial Intelligence in recruiting erupted into a storm that flooded a number of HR conferences. Artificial Intelligence is the newest development in the talent business, and it is fair to say that it will not be going anywhere in the coming years. It's difficult to overestimate this technology's potential for enhancing the conventional recruiting process. Digital assistance, for example, enables businesses to render complex and time-consuming processes much easier and quicker. AI technologies appear to be very promising because they allow recruiters to create cohesive profiles from large unstructured data sets, matching skill sets needed for a specific position.

THE IMPORTANCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENT IN RECRUITMENT

- 1. Time saving:** By maintaining data that don't repeat the same event, artificial intelligence can save time. To fill the necessary time to read through candidate summaries, the traditional recruitment process is used. Therefore, screening resumes is a time-consuming process.
- 2. Talents mapping:** Artificial intelligence helps HR to gain the best talent for the business. It also focuses on competence-based candidates to put them in the right place with the right talent.
- 3. Cost saving:** The role of acquiring the right aspirant for the company is carried out in a qualitative way, and the use of a recruiting firm is minimized. As a consequence, Artificial Intelligence resources assist in cost reduction.
- 4. Hire with Quality:** The Artificial Intelligence tool operates in such a way that it uses massive amounts of data for recruiting and conducts impartial screening and selection. As a result, it leads to the recruiting of eligible applicants.
- 5. Query redressing:** Employees receive up-to-date information and prompt answers to their inquiries. It eventually contributes to employee satisfaction and, as a result, employee engagement. It also contributes to a lower employee turnover rate and ensures that the company receives good support.
- 6. Unbiased recruitment:** Candidate selection is done entirely by computers, with no human intervention. As a result, it results in impartial screening and applicant selection.
- 7. Quality aspirants:** Artificial Intelligence software assists in the screening and selection of eligible applicants. It aids in identifying candidates' abilities, competencies, and traits that are relevant to the job being applied for. As a result, a talented candidate is recruited.

BENEFITS OF USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN RECRUITMENT

1. Improve the Quality and Objectivity of Recruitment

The recruiter is still prejudiced on a personal level. For instance, recruiter A will hire a candidate that recruiter B wouldn't even consider inviting to a job interview. A lot of people are employed based on their feelings, and criteria are frequently arbitrary.

2. Attract the Right Candidates and Receive Less Irrelevant Applications

Any company's job of recruiting the best candidate is crucial. Despite the fact that there are various methods for attracting applicants and that new methods are frequently introduced, job advertisements remain common.

3. The quality of hiring increases

From a huge pool of applications, HR professionals must select the top applicants. Thanks to artificial intelligence, the entire procedure can be automatically divided into numerous parts. By gathering more information about each applicant, recruiters will be able to evaluate them more precisely. There are numerous AI-based solutions available that use unique algorithms to assess candidates' qualifications. The ability to select candidates based on their qualifications

and place them in the appropriate position where their abilities are most needed lies with HR managers. This novel strategy encourages job applicants to advance their abilities while also increasing business productivity. Furthermore, AI software has a better level of accuracy than human recruiters.

4. Automation saves time

The employment sector is no different from other businesses in that it values its time. A candidate's abilities can be evaluated using a range of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools. AI-based apps have the ability to quickly analyse massive amounts of data and come to findings that decision-makers can accept. AI technologies also save money and energy in addition to time.

5. Decisions made without prejudice

AI solutions may help to lessen the bias that human involvement frequently results in, which is a problem that affects all kinds of enterprises. Companies have a fantastic opportunity to choose only the best candidates based on their genuine talent and personality because all decisions are made entirely on the basis of data and resumes.

REVIEW

Vasile Gherhes (2018) has published an article on “Artificial Intelligence: Perception, expectations, hopes and benefits”. In the future, artificial intelligence will have tangible advantages. The author stressed that AI-assisted sophisticated robots will form the future, and that new occupations will emerge. The problem of replacement by robots is now a hot topic, and his research looked at how this replacement would contribute to the creation of new skilled workers and to the growth of new businesses. The article concluded that while AI's emergence and growth were seen as a threat to life and employment, AI's true aim was to better our work, make our lives more comfortable and solve complex problems faced by society. Jiachao Fang et.al. (2018) investigated an initial search of existing literature to definitions of Human intelligence and artificial intelligence. The study identified various types of AI and evaluated each one's results. Finally, it was concluded that AI would ever exceed HI. The author believed that because of cognitive abilities such as emotion detection and imagination, we

cannot assume that machines have surpassed humans. Finally, they claimed that AI will inevitably exceed humanity in any way when super intelligence progresses from a theory to a reality. They also suggested that ongoing research into AI efficiency and comparisons between AI and HI are undertaken.

Geetha et al, (2018) conducted a research on the titled recruitment through artificial intelligence: a conceptual study. The author stated that in this competitive age, an industry or a corporation or a company needs a high quality staff that fulfils its objectives. Both of them are at the start of the fourth industrial revolution. All are looking for bright, potential and dynamic staff to stay competitive in this new environment. In order to navigate the digital world and build business conditions, organisations with a successful recruiting plan may hire suitable person. For any company in recruiting qualified staff, the recruitment strategy can be the main factor in achieving the job goals. As a major feature of the organisation, the recruiting policy is apparently based on the study of data in decision making processes. Data processing is considered to play a decisive role in the recruiting decision as "Artificial Intelligence." Artificial intelligence is an intelligent human development machine in the most basic language. AI can function and respond as human beings, and the ultimate objective is to make it easier for machines to perform as humans usually do. With amazing pace and precision, AI leads. This paper mainly seeks to explore how the recruiting approach is influenced by artificial intelligence. The research also sheds light on AI companies' recruitment strategies. This research is completely carried out on the basis of subsequent sources of knowledge such as philosophical papers, different peer-reviewed journal article, books and websites.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Human recruiters actually perform the bulk of the recruiting process, sifting through CVs, online profiles, and other outlets to identify applicants. Recruiters handle all initial communication, provide input to rejected applicants, and perform candidate interviews. The techniques for investigating technology-based recruiting have been described as missing and lagging behind current practice. As a consequence, more in-depth scientific research in the future with regard to emerging technology that allows for greater versatility and access than before is expected.

RESEARCH AIM AND OBJECTIVE

The aim of this research paper is to determine the effect that artificial intelligence (AI) will have on the recruitment industry over the next five years, with a particular emphasis on how this technology will affect the experience of both employers and applicants.

- 1) To study the opinion on fairness about artificial intelligence usage in recruitment process
- 2) Provide insight into the influence Artificial Intelligence will have on the recruitment industry

- 3) Make recommendations that add value to recruiters considering the introduction of AI technologies into their existing practices

Need of the study

Recruitment, on boarding, rewards, insurance, payroll, and other HR functions are included. In the recruiting process, however, automation is critical. By automating all of the operations, AI decreases the workload of recruiting managers and professionals. Recruiters can save time and focus on other company tasks until it is implemented. A work opening attracts a large number of resumes. It's a difficult task to go through them all and find the ones that are important. Recruiters have a tendency to overlook and misplace several resumes during this phase. As a result, you end up with poor hires. Recruiting necessitates the use of technology. Manual resume preparation is inefficient when recruiters must fill a position in a short period of time.

Scope of the Study

There are very few research-based papers on AI and its integration in HR, despite the fact that there are several articles on the topic. As a result, there is a scarcity of academic studies on AI integration in HR and its benefits. This analysis, which is focused on qualitative research, contributes to the development of AI and HR theory. The study's findings indicate how many HR tasks have incorporated AI and how doing so has increased their efficiency and performance. According to the survey, enterprises, HR specialists, and employees all benefit from the adoption of AI. The outcomes show why all firms should include AI into all HR-related tasks. Researchers can better comprehend the various AI technologies utilised in HRM operations thanks to this study, which also provides insight into respondents' opinions on AI in HRM. The impact of AI-powered HR impacts on work-life balance is attempted to be evaluated.

Research Methodology

Primary data were used by the researcher. A quantitative approach based on the survey method was used to conduct the current study. The Google Forms platform was utilised to administer the questionnaire that served as the data collection instrument (an online survey service). The respondents included HR employees and HR specialists from Chennai-based businesses. The sample size is the number of samples used for the analysis. The sample size for this study is 200 participants. 200 respondents in all were chosen from the company using a straightforward convenience sample technique. Additionally, secondary sources, including books, websites, journals, and magazines, were employed to compile more pertinent information and data.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

In this chapter an in depth study has been made to identify the opinion on fairness about Artificial Intelligence usage in Recruitment Process. For this purpose, primary data was collected from 200 respondents by way of convenience sampling.

Table no 1: Respondents’ opinion on fairness about artificial intelligence usage in recruitment process

Designation	Opinion on Fairness about Artificial Intelligence Usage in Recruitment Process			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Senior executive HR	39 (56.5%)	02 (2.9%)	28 (40.6%)	69
HR executives	12 (37.5%)	05 (15.6%)	15 (46.9%)	32
Trainee associate HR	29 (29.3%)	33 (33.3%)	37 (37.4%)	99
Total	80	40	80	200

Source: Primary Data

It is evident from the above table that the percentage of high level of respondent opinion on the using of artificial intelligence in judging applicant resume instead of human intervene was the highest (46.9%) among the respondents of HR executives and the same was the lowest (37.4%) among the Trainee associate HR. Similarly, the percentage of medium level of respondent was the highest (33.3%) among the respondents of Trainee associate HR and the same was the lowest (2.9%) among the respondents Senior executive HR. On the other hand, the percentage of low level of respondent was the highest (56.5%) among the respondents senior executive HR and same was the lowest (29.3%) among the respondents Trainee associate HR. It may be concluded from the above analysis that the maximum level of respondent opinion on the using of artificial intelligence in judging applicant resume instead of human intervene was senior executive HR.

In order to find the relationship between of the respondent’s designation and their opinion on the using of artificial intelligence, the following null hypothesis was framed and tested with the help of Chi-square test, and the result is shown in the following table

H₀: There is no significant difference between designation of the respondents and their opinion on the using of artificial intelligence.

H₁: There is a significant difference between designation of the respondents and their opinion on the using of artificial intelligence.

Table no 2: Designation and opinion on the using of artificial intelligence

Source	DF	SS	MS	F	S
Between Groups	7.038	2	2.519	3.583	Significant at 5% level
Within Groups	379.889	198	.703		
Total	386.927	200			

It is highlighted from the above table that the calculated F value is greater than the table value and the result is significant at 5% level. Hence, the hypothesis “Designation” of the respondents

and opinion on the using of artificial intelligence” is rejected. From the analysis, it is concluded that there is a significant difference between the using of artificial intelligence of the respondents.

Future AI in Recruitment

The easiest way to communicate with candidates is via chat bots. In reality, it is they who start the distribution of the candidate's experience.

- 1) Personalization is the cornerstone of a positive candidate experience. Future predictive recruiters can use predictive recruiting analytics to close jobs quicker than they can with manual employee assessment.
- 2) The candidate's actions can be anticipated in the future, resulting in faster hiring decisions. In the recruiting process, virtual reality is a disruptor. It's a fantastic way to give candidates a memorable experience. This idea helps candidates to sit in a single location and get a sense of what it's like to work in a high-tech world.

CONCLUSION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a technology which can work in a variety of situations as intelligently as a human brain. In contrast to traditional recruitment methods, the automation of recruiting processes has an increased interest and value. Recruitment is the most critical business to be focused on for every organisation. Now the recruiting industry is gaining momentum with the introduction of a more intelligent approach to recruitment, namely artificial intelligence hiring. In addition, different firms pay attention to changes in the recruitment process. Intelligence artificial technology has a significant impact on recruitment because it assists recruiters in aligning unstructured candidate bio data, generating standardised profiles, and defining and matching industry skill sets. Recruiters claim Artificial intelligence technology competes with them in today's world for recruitment operations. Artificial intelligence will develop impartial and fairness and make it easier to find a job, which will increase the candidate's experience. It is human-made software; however, that makes the process smoother. In summary, the role of artificial intelligence in the combination of human and AI helps organisations maintain their records, save their time and money, and increase accuracy and access to the overall recruitment process. The results show that AI is still a relatively new field of recruitment, with few companies using AI in all aspects of their hiring. In order to incorporate AI in traditional recruitment, recruitment activities, such as the pre-selection and interaction with candidates and submitting recruitment results to candidates are the best bits. Artificial intelligence's main benefits have been referred to as increased productivity and the elimination of repetitive tasks, whereas company readiness to implement emerging technology was the main barrier. Recruiters today believe that AI technology is competing with them for recruitment. However, human-built software makes the job easy when the procedure is being conducted. The combination of people and AI leads to data maintenance saves organisations time and costs with greater precision and provides access to the full recruiting process to complete the AI feature.

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